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**FORMATION OF A NEW PARADIGM FOR THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
OF INTERNATIONAL TRADE IN THE CONTEXT OF GEOPOLITICAL CHANGES
AND TRANSFORMATION OF THE GLOBAL ECONOMIC SYSTEM**

The current stage of global economic development is characterized by profound structural transformations caused by geopolitical changes and technological innovations. Traditional approaches to economic management are losing their effectiveness, and globalization, which previously provided economic growth, is facing problems of depletion of natural resources, environmental degradation and social inequality. All this highlights the need to create a new paradigm for the sustainable development of international trade. The study is based on a comprehensive and systematic approach, which provides for the analysis of international trade trends, assessment of the state of Russia's foreign trade and identification of possible development scenarios in the context of geopolitical instability. Methods of analysis and synthesis, temporal and spatial analysis, as well as specific empirical data are used. The article provides a detailed analysis of modern international trade, with special attention paid to the transformation of the global economic system. The key areas of sustainable development are considered, including the role of digital technologies and artificial intelligence in increasing the competitiveness of international trade. The influence of Western sanctions policy on regional integration and the dynamics of Russian-Chinese cooperation is investigated. The structure of Russia's foreign trade is analyzed separately, and the importance of agriculture in the development of exports is emphasized. The study showed that the new paradigm of sustainable development involves a transition from a linear economy to a sustainable economy, which minimizes negative environmental impacts and supports balanced economic growth. In the context of geopolitical instability, the role of regional integration and the formation of multilateral alliances, such as BRICS, is increasing. For Russia, active participation in international trade, the development of cooperation with BRICS partners and adaptation to changing global market conditions are of key importance.

Keywords: sustainable development, international trade, BRICS, artificial intelligence, agriculture, climate change, global value chain.

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